

A New Synthesis of 6-Acetylbulliferone

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6-Acetylbulliferone required as the starting material for a synthetic work currently in progress in our laboratory¹ could not be prepared in substantial amount by Fries rearrangement of 7-acetoxycoumarin. The product obtained by the method, was always the more probable 8-acetylcoumarin. In fact, we could not isolate any 6-acetyl derivative by employing the method of Shah and Shah².

For the synthesis of 6-acetylbulliferone, we have devised the following method. 3,4-Dihydrobulliferone (I), prepared by condensing acrylonitrile and resorcinol in presence of zincchloride and dry hydrogenchloride³, was condensed with acetic anhydride in the presence of aluminiumchloride and dry hydrogenchloride at 150°. The product 6-acetyl-3,4-dihydrobulliferone (II), m.p. 136° was dehydrogenated with Pd/C to 6-acetylbulliferone (III), m.p. 175°, (Lit.² m.p. 177°).

That the compound melting at 175° is not 8-acetylbulliferone is proved by mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample of 8-acetylbulliferone (m.p. 167°) obtained by Fries rearrangement of 7-acetoxycoumarin, when a depression in m.p. was observed. The ketonic carbonyl band is observed at 1635 cm⁻¹ as in case of 6-acetyl-4-methylbulliferone, whereas the band for both 8-acetylbulliferone and its 4-methyl homologue is observed at 1620 cm⁻¹.

The structure of II has been established as follows.

1. D. K. Chatterjee and K. Sen, communicated.
2. D. N. Shah and N. M. Shah, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 1681.
3. E. Chapman and H. Stephen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127**, 885.

II on Clemmensen's reduction produced 6-ethyl-3,4-dihydroumbelliferone (IV), m.p. 122°. The compound IV was also obtained by condensing 4-ethylresorcinol (V) and acrylonitrile in presence of zincchloride and dry hydrogenchloride.

6-Ethyl-3,4-dihydroumbelliferone on dehydrogenation gave 6-ethylumbelliferone (VI), m.p. 154° (Lit.⁴ m.p. 156°); λ_{max} at 336 m μ (log ϵ 4.18) corresponds to the band of umbelliferone⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were repeatedly crystallized until constant melting points and single spots on TLC were obtained.

6-Acetyl-3,4-dihydroumbelliferone (II): Finely powdered anhydrous aluminium-chloride (8 g., 0.06 mole) was added slowly to a vigorously stirred mixture of 3,4-dihydroumbelliferone (8.2 g., 0.05 mole), acetic anhydride (9 ml, 0.09 mole) and ether (70 ml) maintaining temperature at 10–15°. Dry hydrogen chloride was bubbled through, when a clear solution was obtained. Ether was slowly removed first at 50–60° and later at 100° in an oil bath when an orange viscous slurry resulted. The temperature was raised gradually upto 155–60°; heating was continued maintaining the current of hydrogenchloride throughout the whole reaction period. After 3–4 hrs the whole mass became a glassy red solid, which was kept as such at room temperature overnight. The mixture was decomposed by boiling with 50 ml 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether and ethereal layer dried over sodium sulphate. The residue, after removal of solvent, on vacuum sublimation (230°/0.8 mm) gave material (6.5 g.) which on crystallisation from alcohol yielded *6-acetyl-3,4-dihydroumbelliferone* (2.8 g; 28%), m.p. 136° (Found : C, 64.24; H, 5.02; Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₄ : C, 64.07; H, 4.89%). The IR spectrum showed bands at 1780 cm⁻¹ (lactone > C = O) and at 1635 cm⁻¹ (hydrogen bonded ketonic > C = O). The mother liquor on evaporation yielded an oil which on crystallization from toluene gave the unchanged parent compound (2.4 g.).

6-Acetylumbelliferone (III): A mixture of 3,4-dihydro-6-acetylumbelliferone (1 g.), 5% Pd/C (1 g) and diphenyloxide (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 hrs. The catalyst was removed from the hot solution. Removal of diphenyloxide by distillation under reduced pressure yielded (0.9 g; 90%) crystalline solid which melted at 175° (Lit.² m.p. 177°) after crystallisation from ethanol (Found : C, 64.71; H, 4.35; Calc. for C₁₁H₈O₄ : C, 64.70; H, 3.95). The IR spectrum showed bands at 1735 cm⁻¹ (coumarin > C = O) and at 1635 cm⁻¹ (hydrogen bonded ketonic > C = O).

6-Ethyl-3,4-dihydroumbelliferone (IV): A mixture of amalgamated zinc (prepared from 4.8 g., zinc wool), concentrated hydrochloric acid (8 ml), water (8 ml), and 6-acetyl-3,4-dihydroumbelliferone (1 g.) was refluxed for 6 hrs. The mixture after cooling was decanted from zinc and extracted with ether. The solvent was removed and the results on vacuum sublimation at 160°/0.8 mm, yielded *ethyl-3,4-dihydroumbelliferone* (0.8 g, 83%), m.p. 122° (crystallized from benzene methanol). (Found : C, 68.93; H, 5.94; Calc. for C₁₁H₁₂O₃ : C, 68.73; H, 6.29%).

4. F. Fujikawa and K. Nakajima, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1951, 71, 67.

5. K. Sen and P. Bagchi, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 316.

The compound IV was also prepared by condensing 4-ethylresorcinol (V, 2.5 g) and acrylonitrile (2 ml) in ether (30 ml) with anhydrous zinc chloride (1 g) as condensing agent. The solution was saturated with dry hydrogen chloride below 10° and kept for 48 hrs. The precipitated iminohydrochloride after removal of the ether was refluxed for 1 hr with water (12 ml). The precipitated oil was extracted with ether; the solvent was removed and the residue on vacuum sublimation yielded a material, which was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally crystallised from benzene to yield (2.3 g), m.p. 122°.

6-Ethylumbelliferone (VI): A mixture of 6-ethyl-3,4-dihydroumbelliferone (1 g.), diphenyloxide (20 ml), Pd/C 5% (0.7 g.) was refluxed for 6 hrs. The catalyst was removed by filtration from the hot solution, and the solvent on evaporation under reduced pressure yielded a solid which after purification by vacuum sublimation (180°/0.8 mm) yielded VI (0.7 g.), m.p. 154° (from benzene) (Lit.⁴ m.p. 156°), Found : C, 69.55; H, 5.36; Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₃ : C, 69.46; H, 5.30; λ max 336 m μ (log ϵ 4.18).

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